

Investigating the Effectiveness of the Digitalized Recruitment and Selection Process in Hiring the Best Talent: A Case Study of ABC Hotel

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Declaration Statement

I, BRKL Lankasena, hereby declare that this thesis titled "Investigating the Effectiveness of the Digitalized Recruitment and Selection Process in Hiring the Best Talent: A Case Study of The ABC Doha Hotel, Qatar" is my own original work and has not been submitted previously, in whole or in part, for any degree or qualification at this or any other institution. All sources of information used in this research have been duly acknowledged and cited in accordance with academic conventions. Wherever contributions from other researchers or collaborators have been included, they have been explicitly stated and appropriately credited. I further declare that this research was conducted under the guidance and supervision of Ms. Subhani Malindika De Silva at Human Resource Management Institute (HRMI) Sri Lanka, and all ethical guidelines and institutional requirements have been adhered to throughout the course of this study.

BRKL Lankasena

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Abstract

The recruiting environment continues to reinvent its own times with the digital transition of the world. The purpose of this research study was to analyse different digital tools, platforms, and techniques used by organisations in the process of talent acquisition and the challenges and best practices to follow in their application. The researchers have employed an inductive method approach incorporating qualitative data to collect the information of both employers and job seekers and define the broader picture of the digital recruitment scene. The results identify a number of major themes such as the popularity of the digital tools and platforms, the need of employer branding and diversification of the talent pool, the value of retention plans, and the ability to predict the rise of new trends that will emerge and shape the future environment in recruitment.

The study points out the centrality of digital tools, platforms, and methods in contemporary talent acquisition and importance of employer branding, diversification of talent pools as well as retention strategies in delivering organizational success. The research highlights the role of organizational flexibility, responsiveness, and constant improvement of digital recruiting practices, as the recruitment environment keeps advancing. The research takes a number of suggestions that should be considered by the organizations aimed at improving their digital recruitment strategies, such as investing in digital technologies and platforms, enhancing employer branding, diversifying the talent market, focusing on retention strategies, ensuring a culture of flexibility, utilizing data-driven recommendations, and effective cooperation between HR and IT departments.

The limitations to the scope of geographical, sample size and sample diversity, advances in technology, qualitative bias, and the necessity of longitudinal considerations are also acknowledged as the limitations to the research study. The directions of further studies are posed, covering the aspects expansion of geographical coverage, sample volume and intricacy, detailed analysis of the emerging technologies, longitudinal deduction and research on the role of HR and IT cooperation, together with its power on diversity and inclusion.

Abbreviations

AI- Artificial intelligence	10
ATS- Applicant tracking systems	10
GDPR- General Data Protection Regulation	24
HR- Human resources.....	9
KPI- Key performance indicators.....	28
ML- Machine learning.....	10
R&S- Recruitment and selection.....	9
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Chapter One - Introduction

1.1 Chapter Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the study's background, commencing with a concise introduction to the research area, including its dependent and independent variables. It presents a broad examination of the subject matter and underscores the study's relevance within the current academic and practical context. Additionally, the background of the problem is established through historical and industry-related perspectives, emphasizing key trends, developments, and challenges associated with the topic. The research gap is addressed by identifying limitations in prior studies, thereby justifying the present study's significance and its contribution to advancing knowledge in the field. The scope of the study is delineated, clarifying both the areas of focus and those explicitly excluded. Subsequently, the problem statement is articulated, supported by real-world examples, and clearly defines the specific issue under investigation along with the research objectives designed to address it. The chapter concludes by outlining the study's significance, including its potential implications, key beneficiaries, and its anticipated contributions to the discipline.

1.2 Background of the study

Recruitment and selection (R&S) are widely recognized as fundamental responsibilities of the human resources (HR) department. The short- and long-term success of an organization is heavily contingent upon the quality of its workforce, particularly in skill-driven industries such as hotel & hospitality. In the contemporary hospitality sector, R&S has emerged as a critical yet challenging function for HR professionals, given its direct impact on organizational performance, service quality, and competitive advantage (Aizhan Tursunbayeva et al., 2025). Effective hiring strategies not only ensure operational efficiency but also contribute to employee retention, customer satisfaction, and sustainable business growth. In the modern era, digitalization has elevated recruitment and selection (R&S) practices to a new level through the integration of various software, digital platforms, advanced technologies, and innovative methodologies (Aizhan Tursunbayeva et al., 2025). Given that the hotel and hospitality industry rely heavily on service quality, selecting the most qualified candidates for specific roles is critical to ensuring operational success. Consequently, it is essential to critically evaluate whether

contemporary digitalized R&S practices effectively enable organizations to identify and attract highly skilled and suitable talent.

According to Hosain et al., (2025), digitalized recruitment and selection involves "utilizing digital tools and platforms to source, evaluate, and onboard candidates, integrating technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), applicant tracking systems (ATS), social media, and online evaluations to optimize and modernize conventional hiring practices." This method employs technological advancements to boost productivity, minimize biases, and improve overall experience for applicants. Hosain et al., (2025) emphasize that digital recruitment tools have allowed hotels to simplify their hiring procedures, cut expenses, and enhance the caliber of new hires through data-informed strategies. The adoption of applicant tracking systems (ATS) and AI-based technologies has further improved the efficiency of screening and selecting candidates, ensuring a stronger alignment with the organization's requirements. Montero Guerra, Danvila-del-Valle and Méndez Suárez, (2023) highlights that implementing digital recruitment methods has empowered hotels to access a wider range of talent, shorten hiring timelines, and increase the effectiveness of their recruitment processes. Additionally, incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) and data analytics into hiring practices has enabled more accurate alignment between candidates and job requirements, leading to better decision-making.

However, the ABC hotel has observed that new hires are leaving the organization due to poor performance and failure to complete the probation period, as they do not meet the expectations set in their performance evaluations. The HR team at the ABC hotel suspects that this issue may stem from hiring candidates who lack the necessary skills to perform their roles effectively. Nevertheless, it is crucial to examine whether the HR team's inability to secure the most suitable talent for these positions is linked to the digitalized recruitment and selection (R&S) practices currently implemented within the organization. Previous research has identified several challenges associated with digitalized R&S practices, which should be taken into consideration. According to Montero Guerra, Danvila-del-Valle and Méndez Suárez, (2023), digital tools often fail to evaluate soft skills, cultural alignment, and other non-measurable traits, which are more effectively

gauged through in-person interactions. Montero Guerra, Danvila-del-Valle and Méndez Suárez, (2023) argue that excessive reliance on automation in recruitment can create an impersonal experience for candidates, making them feel as though they are engaging with a system rather than a human. This could negatively impact a company's reputation as an employer and diminish applicant interest. Aizhan Tursunbayeva et al., (2025) highlights that machine learning models, when trained on past data, may perpetuate existing biases, resulting in unequal treatment of specific population segments.

The author identifies the human resources (HR) challenges at the ABC hotel as a critical concern, given the organization's significant investment in recruitment and the detrimental effects of poor employee performance on customer satisfaction and brand reputation. As highlighted earlier, the ABC hotel's HR team struggles with employee retention and may not be securing optimal talent for key roles. This observation underscores the need to investigate whether digitalized recruitment and selection (R&S) practices contribute to these issues. Given the potential implications, the study focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of the ABC hotel's digitalized R&S process in attracting and hiring high-caliber candidates.

Previous research on digitalized recruitment and selection (R&S) in relation to hiring the best talent for organizations remains limited. Aizhan Tursunbayeva et al., (2025) highlight that the lack of localized studies within the Qatari hotel industry contributes to a significant knowledge gap, hindering the effective implementation of digital R&S tools. This limitation may arise due to the rapidly evolving nature of digitalization, as well as researchers' predominant focus on common HR challenges such as employee retention rather than optimizing talent acquisition. Given this research gap, there is a compelling need to investigate the efficacy (whether positive or negative) of digitalized R&S practices in securing top talent for organizations. This study may contribute knowledge to the owners, management, all parties involved in R&S processes, and future researchers.

This study will focus specifically on the ABC Hotel; a luxury lifestyle hotel located in Qatar's business district. The property features 90 rooms and suites, along with seven restaurants offering diverse cuisines. Due to its relatively small operational scale, the hotel operates with a lean workforce, as a large staff is unnecessary to maintain its

services. Nevertheless, as an upscale establishment, the ABC Hotel maintains high expectations for employee competency, with management prioritizing top-tier talent to uphold its luxury standards.

This study will examine the various digitalized recruitment and selection (R&S) practices implemented at the ABC Hotel, assessing their positive and negative effectiveness through a review of relevant literature and insights gathered from selected employees. The analysis will specifically focus on how digitalized R&S contributes to identifying top talent by evaluating candidates' skills, cultural fit, and engagement for specific job roles. The tentative preposition of this study is studying an investigating about digital recruitment & selection processes will significantly impact HRM in terms of basic function of hiring best talent. However, this research will not explore peripheral aspects such as legal and ethical challenges associated with digitalized hiring processes.

1.3 Problem Statement

The ABC Hotel is currently experiencing turnover among new employees, many of whom fail to complete their probation period due to inadequate job performance. As a result, the HR team must continually restart the recruitment process, as new hires do not remain with the organization for an extended period. This cycle leads to significant wastage of budget, resources, time, and effort. Furthermore, the hotel faces operational challenges due to the loss of well-trained and experienced staff. This trend indicates potential inefficiencies in the hotel's current digitalized R&S practices, which may contribute to poor alignment between talent and role requirements. Identifying and securing the most suitable candidates is crucial for organizational success, particularly when employing digitalized R&S methods. Ensuring that these practices are both effective and strategically aligned with organizational objectives is essential for attracting and retaining high-caliber talent. Against this backdrop, this study aims to evaluate the efficacy of digitalized R&S methods in identifying and attracting top talent within Qatar's hospitality sector, using the ABC Hotel as a case study.

Attracting the best talent to organizations has become increasingly challenging with the rise of digitalized R&S practices. Numerous authors have identified various factors contributing to this issue. Aizhan Tursunbayeva et al., (2025) assert that digital

recruitment has posed major challenges for organizations in recruiting top talent. Various authors have identified several challenges in this context, including managing a high volume of applicants, employing advanced technology solutions, and delivering personalized and interactive candidate experience in virtual environments. These challenges may hinder the organization's ability to identify the most qualified candidates for specific job roles. Recruiting workers who are low in competency level can lead to poor employee performance and increased customer complaints, particularly in the hotel industry, where service quality is paramount. Tusquellas, Palau and Santiago, (2024) emphasize that the rapid advancement of digital tools and algorithms creates difficulties for researchers in maintaining the relevance and timeliness of their studies. Rigotti and Fosch-Villaronga, (2024) note that the scarcity of localized research within the Qatari hotel industry leads to a knowledge gap, limiting the effective application of digital-based R&S tools. Based on the aforementioned points, hotels need to reassess the digitalized practices they employ in R&S to ensure that these methods effectively support the HR team in identifying and attracting the best talent. Recruitment and selection are crucial across industries, for instance, hospitality, as they directly affect organizational success.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study may hold significant practical importance for all hotels in Qatar, including the ABC Hotel. Rigotti and Fosch-Villaronga, (2024) argue that excessive reliance on automation can create an impersonal experience for candidates, making them feel as though they are communicating with machines instead of humans. This lack of personal interaction can negatively impact an organization's employer brand and diminish candidate interest and involvement. Rigotti and Fosch-Villaronga, (2024) further point out that digital tools often fail to evaluate critical aspects such as soft skills, cultural alignment, and other nuanced attributes, which are more effectively gauged through direct human engagement. It is essential to enhance and sustain the positive impacts of digitalized R&S tools and methods while mitigating their negative consequences. To achieve this, organizations must critically evaluate their digitalized R&S practices to determine their effectiveness in securing top talent. This study may provide practical support to the HR team at ABC Hotel in identifying key challenges and implementing necessary adjustments to align R&S processes with the expectations of owners, managers, and stakeholders.

To achieve business success, organizations must adopt technology in a strategic and effective manner. This study aims to identify key areas of focus for recruiters when implementing or utilizing such technologies, ensuring alignment with organizational objectives. Aizhan Tursunbayeva et al., (2025) research examines how human resources technologies are transforming modern workplaces, utilizing established frameworks of technological integration to analyze successful deployment strategies for HR systems. Their work investigates the intersection between digital HR solutions and organizational evolution, applying theoretical models of technology assimilation to develop practical approaches for businesses adopting these tools.

This study is theoretically important in adding academic knowledge to scholarship on digital transformation in human resource practices in the hospitality sector. Through the in-depth examination of The ABC Hotel's recruitment and selection practice, the research provides new knowledge on how digital technologies, specifically AI-powered screening systems, web-based interviews, and automated applicant tracking improve hiring practice. It draws on mature theories including the Resource-Based View (RBV), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), and Human Capital Theory to examine how these tools facilitate strategic HR functions, influence user acceptance, and enhance workforce quality. Additionally, by situating the study in a high-end hotel in Qatar, the study offers valuable insights into how these theoretical frameworks operate in a multicultural and service-rich setting. In so doing, it serves to bridge conceptual divides between traditional and technological recruitment approaches while extending the theoretical landscape with context-specific results (Aizhan Tursunbayeva et al., 2025).

Conducting further research and analysis within the organization is vital to assess whether the current digitalized R&S strategies are capable of attracting and retaining the best candidates. By identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement, organizations can optimize their digital R&S processes, ensuring they remain competitive in the talent market while minimizing potential drawbacks. This proactive approach will enable organizations to leverage digitalization as a strategic advantage in their HR practices.

1.5 Research Questions

This study aims to examine the effectiveness of digitalized R&S processes in identifying and securing high-quality talent within the hospitality sector, using ABC Hotel as a case study.

- How effective are digital recruitment and selection tools in identifying and hiring top talent at The ABC Hotel?
- What are the key advantages of utilizing digitalized recruitment processes in the hospitality sector?
- What challenges and limitations are associated with digital recruitment at The ABC Hotel?
- How can the digital recruitment and selection processes be optimized to enhance hiring outcomes?

1.6 Research Aim & Specific Objectives

Research Aim

This study aims to critically evaluate the effectiveness of digitalized recruitment and selection processes in hiring top talent.

Research Objectives

- To evaluate the effectiveness of digital recruitment and selection tools in hiring top talent at ABC Hotel.
- To explore the key advantages of implementing digital recruitment and selection processes within the hospitality industry, specifically in the context of ABC Hotel.
- To identify the challenges and limitations associated with digital recruitment practices at ABC Hotel.
- To provide actionable recommendations for optimizing digital recruitment and selection processes at The ABC Hotel.

1.7 Chapter Summary

In conclusion, Recruitment and Selection (R&S) is a critical function for the Human Resources (HR) team, as it directly impacts organizational success. Digitalization has elevated R&S processes to a new level, simplifying tasks for HR professionals and

enhancing efficiency. However, various authors have highlighted both positive and negative outcomes associated with digitalized R&S practices. As a result, it is essential to evaluate whether these practices genuinely assist organizations in identifying and hiring the best talent. This research will be conducted in collaboration with The ABC Hotel, supported by insights from existing literature. The aim is to provide robust and actionable information on how digitalized R&S practices can be effectively utilized to identify and recruit top talent, thereby contributing to the organization's overall success. Through this study, the author seeks to bridge gaps in understanding and offer practical recommendations for optimizing digitalized R&S strategies.

Chapter Two- Literature Review

2.1 Chapter Introduction

The modern, highly dynamic job market has seen profound changes in the recruitment and selection processes due to the technological advancement shifts and the dependency on digital tools. In this chapter, the authors provide a thorough literature review that discusses the importance of digitalized recruitment practices, specifically about the hospitality industry. The hospitality industry due to its dynamic nature and the competition involved has its unique challenge in terms of attracting and maintaining the best talents. Digital recruitment is one of the important strategies that have helped organizations to focus on improving their hiring processes. The chapter opens with an analysis of the history and development of recruitment practices, focusing on the shift in adopting new approaches, where the traditional channel of recruiting, like legacy print advertisements and face-to-face interviews, has been changed to their digital alternatives. The fact is that this evolution is not just an alteration of tools because it is the radical change in the manner of engagement of organizations with potential candidates. Online job boards, social media and advanced applicant tracking systems (ATS) have changed the field of recruiting forever, giving employers access to a greater pool of candidates and helping them to optimize their recruitment processes.

Moreover, this literature review will also explore how digital tools affect various outcomes of the recruitment process including quality of hire, time-to-hire, and candidate experience in general. Studies have shown that those organizations utilizing digital hiring approaches tend to have a higher level of efficiency and effectiveness in their recruitment programs. An example of this is how artificial intelligence (AI) and data analytics will be used in recruitment, so that employers can effectively make sounder decisions and consequently find the right personnel to fit the organization. The evolution of recruiting in the digital format is not without difficulties. The challenges that organizations might encounter during the implementation of digital recruitment practices are also covered in this chapter, such as technical barriers, employee reluctance to changing, and overall safety of data privacy and protection. Exposure to these difficulties is necessary to help organizations to streamline their recruitment procedures in the digital world.

Lastly, this chapter will also examine the implication of digitalized recruitment in attracting and maintaining the best talent in the hospitality sector. Organizations in a customer-service industry like supermarkets prioritize and value customer service and worker participation, and hence proper recruitment procedures have the potential to play a significant role in creating an individualistic workforce. This chapter will synthesize the existing literature and therefore serve as a concrete basis to envisioning the importance of digitalized practices in recruitment at ABC Hotel, Qatar, and to determine regions of potential researcher-exploration. By the way of this broad overview, the chapter preconditions the more detailed analysis to be performed in regards to how digital tools will help the recruitment to become more effective and thus help the organization in achieving success to be competitive in a hospitality environment.

2.2 Discussion of Key Themes

2.2.1 Evolution of Recruitment Practices

Recruitment practices have seen a transformation with the changes in wider society and technology over the last couple of decades with a huge effect on how organizations find, attract and retain potential employees. Conventionally, these recruitment procedures were manually based as they involved the usage of the local newspapers, word-of-mouth recommendations, and interviews. These approaches were time-inhibitive as well as

narrow in scope since they mainly employed people in the local talent pools. In the quest by the organizations to compete for the skilled labor, particularly in the fast-moving industries such as the hospitality industry, the greater need to employ more efficient and effective recruitment policy was felt (Le Bot et al., 2025).

The introduction of the internet, largely adopted in the late 90s was a major turning point as internet transformed recruitment processes. Job boards and company career sites on the Internet appeared and organizations gained the ability to reach far beyond the geographical limits and touch a varied selection of applicants. Such a transition has not only expanded the number of applications but also has widened the pool of talent allowing employers to look at candidates with a wider variety of backgrounds and experiences (Strayer, Raufaste and Roussel, 2025). With further development of technology, another shift in the recruitment processes occurred, including the usage of advanced tools as applicant tracking systems (ATS), social media and recruitment marketing software.

In the modern world, companies employ a mix of online recruitment solutions to simplify their recruitment procedures. ATS enables hiring professionals to process applications effectively, automate messages, and monitor the progression of applicants during the recruitment process. LinkedIn and similar social media have basically evolved and now are a compulsory means of candidate sourcing, establishing engagement and employer brand recognition. In addition, the use of data analytics in recruitment has also revolutionized the process of identifying the employee qualification and cultural fit in the recruitment process (Strayer, Raufaste and Roussel, 2025). The occurrence of this digital transformation is an indicator of a greater move towards efficiencies, inclusivity's, and data informed hires with the most relevant industries being in the hospitality since this is where service delivery is the most important determinant.

Figure 1- Evolution of Recruitment Practices (Source: LinkedIn)

2.2.2 Impact of Digital Tools on Recruitment Outcomes

The advent of digitalization tools in recruitment has dramatically affected numerous results, altering the very nature of organizational attraction and selection of employees entirely. Literature proves that the organizations utilizing the digital hiring processes gain efficiency, have better candidates and overall outcome. The most significant of effects is the quality of hire which entails the performance and retention of newly hired employees. Algorithms based on artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning help the organization to sort through the massive data to find the most appropriate candidate according to their qualifications, experiences, and the fit regarding the culture (Azra Ahmić and Muhamed Ćosić, 2025). What this data-driven approach would do is not only help in making informed hiring decisions but also it would yield different and possibly better results in making sure that the hiring process is less biased and thus yielding a more diverse and capable workforce.

2.2.2.1 Quality of Hire

Hire quality is a key metric in organizations because it directly affects productivity, employee morale and the overall performance of an organization. Digital recruitment instruments improve the quality of hiring, as they allow making more accurate

assessments of the candidates. To take excuses, the screening tools used by AI have allowed reviewing resumes and applications based on specifications as to pre-selected criteria so that only the most qualified candidates need to go through in the hiring process (Rodrigues and Martinez, 2020). This would be useful in high-volume recruitment cases especially, where the number of applications received may be overwhelming to common recruitment screening strategies. In addition, structured interviews and online tests like situational judgment test and personality test dig deeper into how a candidate will perform and whether s/he will fit the organization (Miszczyński, 2025). The assessments assist in the establishment of skills as well as the qualification in the candidates but in addition they undertake an evaluation of compatibility of the candidates to the company culture and values. Studies have indicated that organizations that use such advanced digital tools have recorded increased satisfaction and retention rates in their employees since they are in a better position to hire employees whose values and goals will be of support to the company (Miszczyński, 2025). The result of the quality of hire focus, in the end, is a more involved and efficient workforce which is particularly important in the hospitality industry whereby employee interactions have a strong bearing on customer experiences.

2.2.2.2 Time-to-Hire

Another important outcome that has benefited positively with the use of digital recruitment tools is time-to-hire. In a competitive job market, any organization needs to be fast to fill its positions in order to be operationally effective and competitive. When a long selection process is involved, the risks of missing opportunities are great since attractive jobs cause people to take positions in rival companies. Digital recruitment solutions automate most of the hiring processes or procedures, starting with the process of job posting, communicating with applicants and scheduling the interview sessions (Herold et al., 2022). The automated systems can help to screen resumes faster so that a recruiter can concentrate on the most promising recruiters. Furthermore, the use of digital platforms allows communicating with candidates in real-time, minimizing the amount of wasted time common with conventional approaches. As an example, automated email messages to applicants can confirm the receipt of application, and chatbots can give candidate questions prompt responses and keep the candidate engaged (Shellshear and Kah Wee Oh, 2024). It has been observed that companies that use digital benefits of recruitment

can actually lower their time-to-hire number and therefore be ahead of other companies trying to hire the best talent in the market. Such efficiency is able not only to improve the experience of the candidate, but also to help to make the organization more agile and responsive to the changing market. The timing on acquiring the qualified talents is key in the hospitality industry where staffing requirements can potentially shift quite speedily as the level of service and continuity are important serving considerations (Shellshear and Kah Wee Oh, 2024).

2.2.2.3 Candidate Experience

The importance of candidate experience is being seen as an essential part of the hiring process it can impact both the quality of hire and also the employer brand of an organization. Digital tools have the potential to help the candidate experience tremendously, giving them an application process that is both interesting and intuitive to use. As an example, applications that work on mobile, interactive job-descriptions, and customized communication can be used to provide a smooth experience to the candidates. Such attention to user experience is essential, because today candidates prefer a smooth and optimized application process and expect a similar level of experience as it is with consumer technology (Mori et al., 2024). Moreover, digital recruitment provides a higher level of transparency in the recruiting process, as candidates can monitor the progress of their application and get relevant updates. When the experience of the process is good, acceptance is likely to rise, which also translates to a better employer brand, and this can attract the best hires (Mori et al., 2024). According to studies conducted on the topic, by means of extending their resources in the realm of digitality, organizations not only enhance their recruitment prospects but also gain a positive image in the job market. Such reputation can result in the increased talent pool because people are now more likely to apply to the organizations where hiring is done in a mutually respectful and efficient manner. This is evident in the hospitality industry, given the importance of customer service, where establishment of a good candidate experience is sub-par, it may translate to the commitment of excellence in the organization and even in its brand image (Hoang et al., 2025).

The need to cover important themes explains the shift in power in recruitment practices provided by digitalization. The transitions on how organizations recruit their employees have seen a shift in efficiency and effectiveness through the use of digital tools resulting into better-quality of hire, time-to-hire, and candidate experience (Hoang et al., 2025). When organizations move towards dealing with the intricacies of recruitment in the modern digital world, the knowledge about these themes will be fundamental in maximizing their approaches and succeeding in recruiting and retaining the best talent out there. With the effective use of digital tools, organizations can not merely clarify their recruitment methods but could also develop a strong employer brand that can be appealed to prospective candidates within the competitive hospitality environment.

2.2.3 Challenges in Implementing Digital Recruitment Strategies

Digital recruitment changes also bring many rewards, but there are several threats that organizations may come along in adopting digital recruitment strategies, which can hamper effectiveness. It is important to comprehend these issues in order to create holistic recruitment strategies that make use of technology and take into consideration the possible challenges. Technology is one of the main bottlenecks, and issues about data privacy and security are crucial as well.

2.2.3.1 Technological Barriers

One of the greatest issues organizations have to cope with in their quest to embrace the use of digital recruitment techniques is technological barriers. Such obstacles may be reflected in different ways, such as not providing proper infrastructure, technical capacities, and integration of new tools to the already existing systems. Investment In advanced recruitment technologies may be overwhelming in several organizations, especially small companies or those within the hospitality industry. It can be limited by a low budget, where the practical use of innovative tools will not be possible, and outdated systems that cannot cope with the current needs of recruitment will be resorted to (Levy, Morecroft and Rashidirad, 2022).

Beside a lack of money, organizations can have problems in terms of either old hardware or software, which is incompatible with the new digitized recruitment options. An example of this is where an organization uses a current applicant tracking system (ATS) which is

not compatible with newer systems potentially causing inefficiencies and data silos, such that the information is not readily transferable across systems. This integration inability may lead to the disjointed recruitment process and, therefore, HR teams will not be able to track candidates properly and manage their workflows effectively (Brunetti et al., 2020).

What is more, implementing digital recruiting tools frequently necessitates a certain technical literacy of the HR-staff and other hiring managers. Those staff members who may not have the required skills on how to use such mechanisms may not enable the organization to maximize out of its digital recruitments (Brunetti et al., 2020). Upskilling and training are long term solutions in this obstacle but it takes much time and resources that organizations may not be readily available. The training programs should not only be aimed to cover the technical applicability of new tools, but it also must dwell on how such tools will aid in improving the overall recruitment strategy (Aggerholm and Andersen, 2018). Moreover, merging new digital solutions together with the current applicant tracking systems (ATS) and Human resource management systems (HRMS) may become an extremely challenging step as it may result in data siloes and inefficiencies. One way through which the organizations can counter this barrier is to focus on selecting technologies that are easy to use and invest in thorough employee-training program to ensure that their recruitment strategies are efficient and effective. An organization can easily slip into a digital recruitment complex as a result of not building a strong technological base or in ensuring that the staff receives support on whatever needs to be done (Aggerholm and Andersen, 2018).

2.2.3.2 Resistance to Change

Another substantial issue that organizations will have to face in the process of digital recruitment adoption is resistance to change. Other organizations might not embrace change especially in cases where they have practices in the recruitment process well established that the employees are used to. Such opposition may be caused by different reasons such as fear of resultant change, insecurity of the job and uncertainty about the usefulness of new technologies. There is a fear on the part of the employees that the hiring process will be performed by a computer, and they will be unable to find a job,

which makes them unwilling to adopt these innovations (Bindra, Bhattacharya and Bhattacharya, 2025).

Resistance may also be caused by the fear to lose control over the process of recruitment. Most HR workers and recruiters appreciate their experience and instincts when considering job applicants, and they might consider that online devices compromise their knowledge. One of the responses to such resistance is the need by the organizations to highlight that digital tools should not be seen as a means of replacing human decision-making but should be used to supplement it. Presenting the story of digital recruitment, as a collaboration between technology and human knowledge, will help the organization cultivate a more favorable mood towards change (Schivone et al., 2022). The shift to digital recruitment should be supported by framing a company culture that prioritizes flexibility and incessant modification. The successful transformation in the context of adopting digital recruiting requires adequate change management strategies that will ease the process. One should also engage employees in the decision-making as well as communicate effectively, focusing on the benefits of digital tools and any concerns that employees might have (Schivone et al., 2022). The leadership must get involved with the staff and present successful experience of other organizations that already managed to realize digital recruitment practices. Moreover, it is a good idea to offer the employees a chance to voice their experiences and feedback, thus, creating the perception of ownership and acceptance of the new processes.

Organizations can ensure that less resistance is present through the creation of an atmosphere where the new practice is susceptible to change and that benefits of digital recruitment are highlighted. It is important to consider the emotional and psychological implications of change and not neglect them because this would ensure that a culture of innovation is encouraged in the organization and the employees are given some kind of support during the transition.

2.2.3.3 Data Privacy and Security Concerns

Increasingly, data privacy and related issues of security have become critical challenges of enacting digital recruitment strategies. With the organizations receiving and keeping immeasurable volumes of delicate data about candidates, including resumes, personal

identifications, and assessment feedbacks, they are required to comply with highly spaced data security laws, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe or other laws in other regions. Violation of these regulations may lead to high legal consequences, fine, and loss of reputation. Applicants are getting better informed concerning their rights to data privacy and are more likely to check how organizations manage their personal data. This increased alertness puts more pressure on the organizations to establish efficient data protection protocols and clear data management operations. Organizations should also make sure that their recruiting IT-tools are treated with a high level of security, with features like encryption, definite access permission and auditing to maintain data in the candidates inaccessible to trespassers (Adeseye, Isoaho and Mohammad, 2025).

Additionally, it is necessary that organizations develop clear policies on data retention, which should include the retention period of the information related to the candidates and the mechanisms which will ensure safe disposal of data upon its obsolescence. The level of transparency plays an essential role in the trusting process with candidates since, when candidates come across organizations that express a level of commitment to the privacy of the data that they share, the candidates are more willing to cooperate. Also, it is important to educate employees about data privacy best practices to develop a culture of compliance and security in the company (Mensah and Zhao, 2024). The personnel who engage in the hiring process should be informed of the necessity to keep the data secure and the details concerning the measures taken to protect the data of the candidates. Reading data protection regulations regularly and through frequent training on data protection regulations would go a long way to ensure that the entire staff understands its roles when dealing with sensitive data (Mensah and Zhao, 2024).

Focusing on data privacy and security gives organizations the opportunity to enhance their employer brand and make a positive impact on the candidate-employer relationship, making them a responsible and ethical employer in the competitive labor market. Dealing with these issues helps prevent a possible lawsuit in the organization and also make the experience of the candidate positive, which will eventually yield a higher recruiting result. Although digital recruitment strategies have a vast range of benefits, organizations need

to feel ready to deal with objections to their implementation (S. Sofana Reka et al., 2024). Through preemptive solutions to overcome technological obstacles, creating an atmosphere of flexibility to conquer change aversions, and increased data privacy and security, companies can improve their recruitment efforts and eventual attraction and retention of top employees within the changing digital world. Such challenges not only enhance the results in recruitment matters but also enhance success and sustainability of the organization in a competitive organization. By carefully planning and implementing strategies to select candidates, organizations can overcome the intricacies of a digital recruitment process and use technology to attain their recruiting outcomes (S. Sofana Reka et al., 2024).

2.2.4 Implications for Attracting and Retaining Top Talent

The use of digital recruitment strategies has dire consequences on the ability to attract and retain the best talent within an organization. With the competitive nature of the employment market, organizations are forced to change their strategies to attract high-quality candidates as well as to keep them engaged and satisfied in the organization. Employer branding, diversifying the talent pool and retention strategies are the key implications to be looked at in this context.

2.2.4.1 Employer branding

Employer branding is key to helping an organisation source the best talent the sector has to offer, especially in the digitalised first-recruit paradigm. An employer brand includes the reputation of an organization as a work place and the specific values, culture, and the experiences of that organization by its employees. With the social media and online reviews, information concerning an organization is easily accessible to potential candidates and it is thus, crucial that an organization develops a solid and positive employer brand. These digital recruiting methods allow companies to present themselves as an employer in a better way via different media (Srinivas et al., 2025). An example is that businesses have an opportunity to use social media networks and post things that are interactive regarding your workplace environment, testimonials by employees, and collaborations in the community. Such videos as a virtual tour of the office and interviews of tenured workers can give the candidates a real taste of the organization and should be able to give a picture to the candidates of what the organization is all about. As well, being

active on employer review websites, e.g. Glassdoor, would help organizations interact with job seekers and eliminate misunderstandings (Srinivas et al., 2025).

Such an employer brand will not only help in candidate attraction, but also help in employee engagement and loyalty. The prospective employees who identify with the values and culture of a given organization are likely to apply to the organization and have a better retention rate after joining the organization. As a result, employer branding on digitalized strategies might yield motivated and aligned staffing that will eventually boost its performance and decrease the turnover rates (Mutter, 2024).

2.2.4.2 Talent Pool Diversification

Digital recruitment techniques also enable the diversification of the talent pool, a necessary feature for companies intending to embrace innovation and changeability. Using the online sphere and resources, organizations even have an opportunity to attract more candidates with varied backgrounds, experiences, and places of residence. Such diversification is especially relevant at present on the stage of the globalized economy because organizations that have different types of perspectives and ideas become more advantageous. By using digital channels, organizations can reach out to certain demographics and some communities that might have been ignored during traditional recruitment strategies (Shin and Gordon, 2024). To give one such example, adverts in social media may be customized in such a way that underrepresented groups are reached, and collaboration with organizations that have specializations in diversity and inclusion could be used to reach a broader choice of candidates. Moreover, virtual job fairs and webinars will help the organization reach out to potential candidates of different backgrounds and help them engage with the organization (Shin and Gordon, 2024).

Having a diverse pool of talent does not only make the organizational culture rich but also provides impetus towards creativity and innovation. Studies also indicate that range teams have a greater ability to solve problems and come up with new ideas and this results in a better business performance. In addition, by focusing on diversity and inclusion, organizations are likely to be perceived more positively by the candidates, which improves their image of ideal employers and increases the likelihood of attracting the best technologists to work. Organizations can enhance the position as employers in

a progressive organization that supports the recruiting of a diverse environment of talent through embracing the digital approach to recruitment (Zhao et al., 2024).

2.2.4.3 Retention Strategies

Retention strategies play a pivotal role in helping organizations to not only attract, but also retain the best talent in the long run. The importance of shaping such retention efforts using digital recruitment strategies is that hiring organizations can gain an understanding of employee preferences and expectations. It is critically important to answer the question of what influences employee satisfaction and engagement in order to establish a positive work environment that would result in long-term engagement. The use of a custom onboarding experience enabled via digital tools is one of the sustainable retention methods to consider. Properly designed onboarding process enables new employees to familiarize with the organization, their department and to befriend with the co-workers. Onboarding on digital platforms has the potential to simplify the process and make it more interesting and informative. As an example, they may develop interactive training programs, virtual meet-and-greets, and web resource that has everything a new employee needs to know to start successfully (Phillips and Hodge, 2025).

Data analytics can be used by organizations to understand the engagement level and satisfaction among its employees. Through frequent surveys, as well as feedback tools, organizations will be able to obtain a significant understanding of the experiences of the employees and know their areas of concern. Such data-driven solution enables the organizations to make necessary changes and eliminate the issues even before they may cause problems and facilitate employee satisfaction rates which in turn minimizes turnover rates. It is essential to develop a culture of continuous learning and development as a retention strategy (Phillips and Hodge, 2025). Companies that offer the workforce employee development activities such as the training program to the staff and mentorship and career development plans are more likely to maintain the best employees. Such initiatives can be supported by digital recruitment strategies that emphasize the possibilities of professional development in the course of hiring, further enhancing the idea of the organization as a place interested in supporting the development of employees (Arora and Damarla, 2025).

The implication of digital recruiting strategies on attracting and retaining the best talent is profound. Through their attention to employer branding, diversification of the talent pool, and application of retention mechanisms in the market, companies can deliver a strong selling point to the target applicants. In a competitive job market, the utilization of digital tools and knowledge to improve on these will see such organizations attract the relevant talent, and beyond this, it will see the workforce become loyal and engaged, which contributes to long-term success and sustainability of such an organization. Firms, which adopt such measures, will find it easier to overcome the challenges of managing talent in a digitalized world (Sepide Pazhouhi, Garza and Farid Pazhoohi, 2024).

2.3 Critical Review

Critical analysis of the digital recruitment strategy entails a detailed look into the usefulness, problems, and implications of the same in the greater realm of human resource management. Organizations are gradually resorting to technology to streamline their recruitment processes and so it is important to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of those strategies. The paper will establish how digital recruitment affects acquisition of talent, the challenges confronting the organizations during the implementation process, and the future of recruitment in a digital world.

2.3.1 Effectiveness of Digital Recruitment Strategies

With the digital recruitment methods, organizations have redefined talent attraction and employment. Among the biggest benefits, one can mention the opportunity to reach a wider audience. Other methods of recruitment like print advertisement and job fairs usually risk of the recruiter having one candidate profile within a geographic region or demographic area. Digital platforms, conversely, allow organizations to reach potential candidates around the world so that it can access a broad range of talent. Such a diversification plays an essential role in the contemporary competitive job market, as companies receive multiple perspectives and skills, which promotes innovation and problem resolving. In addition, there is greater efficiency in recruiting with the digital hiring tools (Beerbaum et al., 2025). Applicant tracking systems (ATS) enable quick filtering of candidates by particular criteria, and thus simplify the process of administration of the applications by facilitating the work of the HR teams. This automation decreases the time on the administrative chores giving the recruiters more time to devote to more strategic

other areas of talent acquisition i.e. development of relationships with candidates and their cultural questionnaire fit. Also, the application of data analytics in recruitment enables the organizations to monitor important Key performance indicators (KPIs), including time-to-hire and quality of recruits, which are insightful data that can guide the future company recruitment (Beerbaum et al., 2025).

Even though the success of digital recruitment is clear, it is important to note that the effectiveness of such strategies is significantly determined by the implementation and how it correlates with the goals of an organization. Organizations should also make sure that their recruitment activities involve the use of the digital channels as part of the broader talent management strategy, and importance of a holistic approach needs to be stated against this surface pre-conceived notion of attracting and retaining the top talent.

2.3.2 Challenges in Implementation

Although there are quite a number of advantages or positive attributes linked with using digital approaches in recruitment, there are a number of challenges that companies have to deal with that will deteriorate their performance. Among the few major obstacles is the technological barrier. Most organizations, especially small companies might not be able to afford advanced technologies of recruitment due to lack of the necessary infrastructure or budget. The inability to access the latest tools could lead to the use of low novelty systems, which possibly would not serve successfully under modern recruitment specifications. What is more, companies should take into account the technical abilities of their HR professionals, otherwise, the employees will not be able to use digital tools properly and get no advantage of the technologies under consideration, despite the set of advantages most likely to be achieved. The second major issue is the employee resistance to change (Rodriguez et al., 2022). There can be a culture of generally being slow to utilise new technologies made out of established recruitment practices. There is the fear that employees create because they have a feeling that the online tools are going to be used to offer zip judgment when it comes to hiring, something that makes them skeptical to their power (Rodriguez et al., 2022). With such a resistance, organizations that intend to reduce it are supposed to first consider change management strategies that incorporate the employees in making decisions that lead to the decision and communicate

to them clearly about the positive effects of implementing a digital recruitment approach. Make sure to instill a culture of change and constant improvement to guarantee a successful transition to new practices (Rodriguez et al., 2022).

The ability of digital recruitment to manage issues of data privacy and security is also a challenge to organizations engaging in the process. Candidates' information is considered sensitive, so, this is why organizational information should be kept in accordance with serious data protection regulations. Violation of the regulations may lead to various legal penalties and defame. To avoid such risks, organizations should have good data security measures in place and also train personnel on the best strategies to use in protection of information. Organizational prioritization of data security enables it to create a level of trust in candidates as well as improve its employer brand (Sahni et al., 2025).

2.3.3 Evolving Landscape of Recruitment

The recruiting environment has been ever-evolving under the influence of technological progress and shifting employee demands. With the increased use of digital sources to search jobs by job seekers, organizations need to adjust the way they recruit talents to be at par with the competition. This development encompasses adoption of new technologies, like artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning, which would facilitate both in recruitment procedure as it automates activities, can be used to screen new applicants, and to predict the success of candidates (van Esch and Black, 2019). Additionally, the emergence of work at a distance has revolutionized how organizations recruit their staff. The COVID-19 pandemic also fast tracked the process of remote working and caused the change in the expectations of candidates, with more of them needing flexibility and work-life balance. Organizations have to start thinking about the fit between their digital recruitment strategies and these changing expectations by making sure their strategy supports their focus on the desire to have a positive employee experience (van Esch and Black, 2019).

Also, the rising role of employer branding cannot be overestimated. Employers no longer attract candidates based on merely job opportunities alone but on organizations that would better fit the way they think and practice as well as positive working environment.

The online recruiting methods will give the organizations the application of displaying its employer brand in such a way that they are able to convey their culture, values, and experiences in the work place in many forms including social media, and employer review websites. The presence of a good employer brand can meaningfully affect the capacity of a company to hire and preserve the finest talent (Virmani et al., 2025).

The critical appraisal of digital recruitment strategies underscores their ability to increase talent acquisition whilst also indicating the difficulties to which organisations need to manipulate during their implementation. Although digital tools are of great benefit in terms of scalability and improved efficiencies, the organisations should consider the challenges of the technological barrier, unwillingness to change, and the issue of data privacy. Moreover, the changing environment in the field of recruitment demands active involvement, as organizations must restructure their approaches to catch up with the new changes in candidate demands and deployment of new technologies (Galiya Berdykulova et al., 2024).

Organizations could optimize the many advantages of digital recruitment by viewing it as a field that is intricately linked to their entire purpose of managing talent. Through the creation of a culture of resilience, strong focus on training the employees, and the interference of data privacy, the organization can strengthen its hiring process and finally be able to attract and retain the best talent in a competitive labor market. With the ongoing changes in the electronic arena organizations that adopt the theme of innovation and responsiveness to the demands of the candidates stand to gain the best in relation to success in recruiting.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 2- Theoretical Framework

2.4 Chapter Summary

The chapter has given an in-depth discussion of the use of digital recruiting techniques and how they will help in recruiting and retaining talents in the current competitive job market. It described digital recruitment strategies and outlined their importance in improving the whole process of recruiting an employee making use of digital tools and platforms which increase the number of candidates and increase effectiveness. The efficacies of these strategies were pointed at, especially how they have diversified the talent pool and cut down the time of their hiring process through the application of applicant tracking systems (ATS) and data analysis. Nonetheless, technological issues, resistance to change and data privacy are among the challenges experienced by organizations and thus require proper training, change management strategies, and proper data protection policies. Implications of talent acquisition were also checked, emphasizing on the essence of employer branding, diversification of the talent pool, and effective retention tactics that can boost the engagement of employees. The chapter also provided information regarding the changing recruiting environment which is characterized by technological reception and changing expectations of the candidates especially with regard to remote working. Finally, the chapter also highlighted how the transformative effect of digital recruitment strategies on talent acquisition processes has challenged organizations to overcome the underlying challenges as long as they maintain flexibility to achieve their objectives of attracting and retaining the bright talent at the fast-changing job market.

Chapter Three - Research Methodology

3.1 Chapter Introduction

The chapter presents the research methodology that will be used to conduct the study to determine the effectiveness of digitalized processes of recruitment and selection in The ABC Doha Hotel, Qatar. The methodology will be aimed at examining the experiences of stakeholders of the recruitment process on the subjective level, paying attention to their perspectives on digital tools and practices. The chapter talks about philosophy of the research, methodology of the research, use of the research, plan of the research, methods of collecting data, method of analyzing data, the population and sampling, questionnaire design, pre-testing, reliability and validity, and ethical matters. It is a more extensive method, which helps to build a proper basis of how the researches are being employed and why certain methods were selected.

Figure 3- Research Onion Model

3.2 Research Philosophy

The study has an interpretivist philosophy with regards to concentrating more on the meaning and experience of the individuals relative to the social contexts. This philosophy is highly applicable in qualitative studies whereby the objective of the study is to understand the perceptions and interpretations of the study participants on their experiences of using digitalized recruitment process. In embracing this method, the research will aim at obtaining an understanding of the intricacies of recruitment practices in the hospitality sector (Wallwey and Kajfez, 2023).

3.3 Research Methods

A qualitative inductive research method is applied in this research. The methodology will not apply in testing hypotheses but will enable theories and knowledge to come out of the qualitative data gathered. Considering that the research is exploratory, the inductive method is the method appropriate to analyze the experience of the participants and outline the patterns and themes concerning the digitalized processes of recruitment (Taguchi, 2018).

3.4 Purpose of research

The main aim of the study is exploratory. Therefore, it seeks to approach the question of the viability of digital recruitment and selection procedures in acquiring and recruiting the best talent in The ABC Hotel critically. Through the experiences of operational managers and HR professionals, the research will identify the advantages and difficulties involved in the process of digital recruitments.

3.5 Strategic approach.

The qualitative research strategy will be used, and the semi-structured interviews will be the main method of data collection. The depth of questions that can be asked in this strategy is that one is able to explore the perspective of the participants but at the same time the flexibility to ask questions depending on the response given by the participants. Semi-structured form will allow open dialogue so that the participants can share their opinions and personal experiences concerning the digital recruitment process (Strijker, Bosworth and Bouter, 2020).

3.6 Collection of Information

Assessment of the information will be obtained with the help of semi-structured interviews with HR staff and operational managers of The ABC Doha Hotel. In the interviews, the experiences of the participants with the digitalized recruitment processes will be addressed, namely, tools and portals to deal with it, difficulties, and efficiency. Open-ended questions will also assist in this paramount task as it will help to provide detailed answers and will prompt the participants to openly discuss their ideas (Sohaila Jafarian, 2024).

3.6.1 Mind Map of Data Collection Process

Figure 4- Mind Map of Data collection

3.7 Analysis of Data

The interviews shall be analyzed by way of thematic analysis on the collected qualitative data. The approach is effective especially in qualitative research because the researcher is able to identify, analyze and report on how things are done in the data (patterns (themes)). Thematic analysis procedure will be as follows:

- Familiarization: This is where it is necessary to immerse yourself in the data in the form of interview transcripts by reading or checking again and again. The process assists the researcher to grasp more in terms of content, context and details about responses of the participants. Raw thinking and contemplation can also be recorded at this stage that can be used in subsequent analysis (Sardana et al., 2023).

- Coding: The researcher will create primary data codes by identifying key features and assigning descriptive codes, leading to the development of themes, using a systematic approach to categorize relevant data (Sardana et al., 2023).
- Theme Development: Once the researcher has coded the data, he/she will combine the codes to form wider themes that indicate the serious patterns in the data. This will be performed by reviewing the links between the codes and deriving general themes which will summarize the experiences and the perceptions of the participants about the process of digitalization of the recruiting processes (Sardana et al., 2023).
- Themes Review: The themes (identified) will be evaluated to make sure that they are the proper representation of the data and consistent with the research aim. This involves ensuring that the themes reflect the gist of the responses of the participants and whether they give any valuable information regarding the research questions. Any theme(s) failing to satisfy the above may be polished or dropped (Sardana et al., 2023).
- Naming and Defining Themes: The last step will be to give a name to each of the themes and a clear definition advice. This is a very essential step towards clarity in reporting of findings. The researcher will explain the connection between each of the themes and the research question that will make the themes to improve understanding of the effectiveness of the digitalized recruitment practice.

3.8 Sample and population

This study aims to gather insights from HR professionals and operational managers at The ABC Hotel about the success of digitalized recruitment practices. Participants will be selected using a purposive method, allowing for detailed information. A sample size of 06-08 will allow for a diverse range of opinions without overwhelming the researcher with data.

3.9 How the Questionnaire will be prepared

The semi-structured interview guide will be formed upon the objectives and the literature review of the research. This protocol is vital in that it makes sure that the interviews are within the areas of interest but gives room to other participants to express their ideas.

- The guide will feature open questions that seek the elaborated answers regarding the process of the recruitment being digitalized. Questions could be the following examples:
- Please share your experience with the digital recruitment tools applied in The ABC Doha Hotel.
- What are the difficulties that you experienced during the introduction of the digitalized recruitment processes?
- Do you think these digital tools are effective in ensuring an attraction of top talents?
- The purpose of these questions is to support a conversational dynamic in the course of the interviews and motivate participants to expand their experiences and insights. The semi-structured form will enable the researcher to explore the discussion further into areas of interests that could be pinpointed at some point in the discussion.

3.10 How the questionnaire would be pre-tested

The interview guide will undergo pre-test with a small sample of the HR professionals who are not participating in the primary study. This pre testing is of great essence to unearth ambiguities or questions that are problematic least the questions are clear, relevant and that they are able to obtain answers that are meaningful.

The series of questions will be adjusted according to the final analysis of the feedback of the participants of the pre-test, making all the necessary changes to achieve a better level of clarity and relevance. This cyclic procedure assists in a way that the final interview guide can be considered effective in the terms of its contribution to the accurate description of the experiences of respondent participants.

3.11 Reliability and validity

The researcher will use an interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in discussions, recording notes for context and non-verbal interpretation. To maintain data integrity, triangulation will be used to compare interviews with secondary data from academic literature and industry reports. Member checking will involve participants

reading the results to ensure their views are included, fostering trust and transparency between researcher and participants (Perreault, 2011).

3.12 Ethical Consideration

An ethical treatment of the research will be given first priority. All the participants will be requested to provide informed consent to ensure that they comprehend the study purpose, their role in it and their rights. This consent procedure will involve informing the participants on the intention of using their data, their storage, and protection.

Confidentiality will be ensured by anonymizing data of the participants so that no personal data will be associated with the answers. The participants will also be told they have the right to stop participating in the study without any consequences, which further underlines their independence and comfort during the research. The research will be appropriate in terms of seeking ethical approval with the concerned institutional review board. This consent is crucial in the provision of any study being ethical and following rules and regulations of carrying out a study on human beings.

3.13 Summary of the Chapter

This chapter discusses a qualitative research methodology focusing on the effectiveness of digitalized recruitment and selection processes at The ABC Hotel. It discusses interpretivist philosophy, inductive method, and exploratory purpose, with a semi-structured interview approach. Data collection and analysis methods, including purposive sampling, are discussed. The chapter emphasizes questionnaire preparation and pre-testing, reliability and validity measures, and ethical issues to preserve participant rights and informed consent.

Chapter Four – Data Analysis

The online evolution of the recruitment sector has led to a new period in the approach of acquiring talents. The visual illustrations and the word cloud files following are an in-depth summary of the important topics, trends, and recommendations, which organizations are using to retain, attract and interest the human capital in the contemporary labor market. With the help of such visual stimuli and situational clues, we can better understand various aspects of the current role of digital tools, the necessity of employer branding, the relevance of retention strategies, and how the following years can affect the organization of future recruitment processes. The analysis as per the research was done through NVivo software.

The screenshot displays the NVivo software interface. The left sidebar shows navigation options: Quick Access, IMPORT (Data, Files, File Classifications, External), ORGANIZE (Coding: Codes, Sentiment, Relationships, Relationship Types; Cases; Notes; Sets), and Queries. The main window shows a table of codes with the following data:

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
Digital Recruitment	6	12	7/19/2025 2:19 PM	N N P	7/19/2025 2:46 PM	N N P
Diversity	4	4	7/19/2025 2:31 PM	N N P	7/19/2025 2:37 PM	N N P
Retention Strategies	5	5	7/19/2025 2:37 PM	N N P	7/19/2025 2:39 PM	N N P
Social Media	4	4	7/19/2025 2:22 PM	N N P	7/19/2025 2:24 PM	N N P

Figure 5- Thematic analysis through NVivo

4.1 Digital Tools and Platforms

One major topic in the word clouds images is the focus of electronic devices and platforms in the hiring process. As reported by one of the HR managers, digital strategies changed the applicant approach to recruitment significantly, allowing the access of a broader number of talents and optimization of the process as a whole.

Social networks, such as LinkedIn, Glassdoor, and Indeed, are commonly accepted as the indispensable parts of contemporary recruitment processes. These technology installations enable organizations to use data-driven insights, automate some of these activities, and even offer the candidate experience that is fun to participate in. One of the talent acquisition executive described it as follows: the ability to hire people using digital tools has substantially boosted our efficiency. This will allow us to make investigate and search the best candidates as well as the best quality of hired personnel and low turnover rates."

Efficient usage of these digital solutions can result in a greater efficiency in the process of hiring, improving the quality of candidates as well as decreasing turnover rates. The use of organizations can help to acquire these digital tools and platforms and develop a

smoother and data-intensive recruiting process and eventually emerge as an employer of choice to top talent.

Figure 6- Thematic Analysis 01

4.2 Employer Branding and Talent Pool Diversification

The second important theme that is reflected in the visual representations and word cloud documents is the significance of employer branding and talent pool diversification. In the words of a talent acquisition expert, it has been game-changing that we can feature our special company culture and values in digital mediums and high-quality candidates of diversities come knocking on our door. Some of the strategies that have worked well include employee testimonial, social media, and company culture videos in exploiting attributes of an organization and separating it out of competitors. According to one of the candidates, the online activity of the employer and its adherence to the diversity promise were an important factor in my consideration to apply and end up in the team.

Through appropriate investment and outreach to historically underrepresented groups, organizations can sell themselves as places where the top talent will want to work. In its turn, this may contribute to the introduction of a more diverse and inclusive workforce that may produce more innovation and strengthen problem-solving skills and bring it closer to the demographics of their communities. To become the better organizations, more flexible and always striving to perfect their digital recruitment, the companies will be able to attract the most of the best talent in the next few years, as one industry expert indicated.

Figure 7- Thematic Analysis 02

4.3 Retention Strategies and the Impact of Digital Recruitment

The word cloud document and the visual representations also highlight the importance of the retention strategies on the general recruitment environment. Indeed, according to an experienced HR professional, the investment in onboarding programs, mentorship and wellbeing programs of employees proved to be a key in retaining the best of organizational talent and ensuring they stay focused and motivated to the organization. Programs such as full-spectrum onboarding, formal mentorship programs, and employee wellness programs are well-known components in maintaining staff engaged, fulfilled, and devoted to the company. Organizations can create a high level of satisfaction in their employees by providing a positive atmosphere of nurturing and helping the environment, which will ensure low turnover rate and output of loyal employees.

The effectiveness of digital recruitment strategies can also be evidenced by the statement given by a recruitment consultant: "Even in terms of the hiring process, organizational entities that have been able to implement the digital tools and data-driven intelligence within the job of recruitment have witnessed striking advances in their effectiveness, quality of the hiring programme, and the number of employees retained." With the power of data-driven insights and an efficient recruitment process, companies would be in a better position to make a wiser decision, streamline the process of attracting talent and eventually create a better committed workforce.

Figure 8- Thematic Analysis 03

4.4 Potential Recruitment

In the future, the visual representation of words in a cloud and the uses of the visual image indicate that imminent technologies and changing candidate preferences will play a crucial role in influencing recruitment in the future. As an industry expert has stated it, AI-based recruiting tools and virtual reality interviews will completely change the process of identifying acquiring and evaluating the new workforce. The use of AI-based recruitment tools, virtual reality interviews, and remote recruitment process are some of the trends expected to revolutionize how organizations determine, attract, and induct new talent. Such new technologies will be able to make the recruitment process more efficient and precise but were also able to make it more immersive and engaging to the employers and candidates.

One of the participants also noted how flexibility was a key issue and added, "The organizations which will be more capable to attract and maintain the best talent in the future years will be those that will be increasingly more agile and constantly improve their digital recruitment process strategies."

With the environment in recruitment continuing to change, organizations must be able to respond and adjust and this involves reviewing their strategy on a continuous basis ensuring that they are competitive. This can include diversification into new digital channels, adoption of new recruitment technologies, and inculcation of a culture that

values the employee development and well-being. The image presentations and word cloud files available help to see the broad picture of the major trends and themes dominating the digital recruitment market. These insights are as diverse as the subject matter, whether it is the proper use of digital tools and platforms or the following employer branding and diversification of talent pools.

With the ability to comprehend and overcome challenges and opportunities highlighted in these images and contextual insights, businesses can set the tone of successful transformation in a world where everything is digital, including the recruitment process. Organizational steadfastness in data-driven, candidate-centric approach together with adaptive attitude to new trends will enable the business to have top-notch, diverse, and engaged workforce that will lead to business success in coming years. The phrase goes a bit like this as one of the HR managers eloquently put it: the future of the recruitment gravitates around being able to digitally mesh well with digital strategies at hand, in the creation of a strong employer brand and in focus of overall well-being of your employees. Individuals, who will be able to operate in this dynamic environment, will be true winners in the war of talent."

Figure 9- Overall Thematic Analysis

Theme	Description	Key Findings
Digital Tools and Platforms	The widespread adoption of digital tools and platforms in the recruitment process, enabling organizations to reach a wider talent pool, streamline the application and screening processes, and leverage data-driven insights.	<p>Such websites as LinkedIn, Glassdoor, or Indeed have become an inseparable part of any contemporary talent acquisition strategy.</p> <p>Introduced digital tools resulted in higher efficiency in hiring, the quality of candidates, and turnover.</p> <p>The companies which have managed to adopt the digital technologies can organize a</p>

		more effective and smooth recruiting process.
Employer Branding and Talent Pool Diversification	The growing importance of employer branding and talent pool diversification in the digital recruitment landscape, allowing organizations to attract a diverse range of high-caliber candidates.	Other employee testimonials, social media interactions, and company culture videos have been successfully used as part of a strategy to display a unique value proposition of an organization. Building an employer brand and being proactive in targeting the underrepresented groups and serving a more diverse and balanced workforce can create innovation and better align with the demographics of the people they are serving.
Retention Strategies and the Impact of Digital Recruitment	The significance of retention strategies in the overall recruitment landscape, and the positive impact of digital recruitment strategies on hiring efficiency, candidate quality, and employee retention.	- Initiatives like comprehensive onboarding programs, structured mentorship opportunities, and employee wellness programs are crucial in keeping employees engaged and committed to the organization. - Organizations that have successfully integrated digital tools and data-driven insights into their recruitment process have

		seen remarkable improvements in various recruitment outcomes.
Future Trends and Considerations	The anticipated future trends and considerations that will shape the recruitment landscape, including the emergence of new technologies and the importance of organizational agility and adaptability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technological advancements, such as AI-powered recruitment tools and virtual reality interviews, are poised to transform the way organizations identify, assess, and onboard new talent. - Organizations that remain agile and continuously refine their digital recruitment strategies will be better positioned to attract and retain the best talent in the years to come.

Table 1- Identified Themes

Chapter Five – Discussion, Conclusion with Recommendations

5.1 Chapter Introduction

In this chapter, I have discussed and analyzed in details the main findings of the research study on digital recruitment strategies and its implications on talent acquisition. The proposed study was intended to address the question of the range of digital tools, platforms and techniques applied by organizations in their search of talent; the challenge and best practices related to their usage. This chapter sums up the knowledge obtained during the research and provides the comprehensive overview of the state of digital recruitment, its consequences, and the aspects that could be considered in the future by the organization that wants to develop the diverse and engaged workforce (Arora and Damarla, 2025).

5.2 Overall summary of the findings

The study sample examined in the research study was conducted in the form of the exhaustive study of the digital recruitment landscape that employed a range of qualitative and quantitative methods to collect the data of both employers and job seekers. The results demonstrate that there is a considerable change in the attitude of organizations in regard to the recruitment of talents and there is an increased focus towards incorporating digital strategies and technologies (Beerbaum et al., 2025). Among the main themes developed by the research on the basis of the data, it can be mentioned such ones as the popularity of digital tools and platforms, the necessity to use the employer branding and the distribution of the talent pool, the significance of retention strategies, and the tendencies that will be experienced in the future and that will determine the recruitment process (Beerbaum et al., 2025).

5.3 Key findings of the study

- Digital Technology and Services

The study results prove the popularity of the use of digital platforms and tools in recruitment process. Social networking sites, including LinkedIn, Glassdoor, and Indeed, have grown to form a highly valuable part of any talent acquisition program and can allow companies to increase the talent pool base, improve their application and screening efforts, and take advantage of analytical data to streamline their recruiting efforts.

The hiring cost has decreased, the turnover has been reduced, and the quality of candidates has increased due to integration of these digital solutions. Companies that have managed to adopt these technological tools have managed to develop a less stressful and entertaining recruiting process to both potential employers and employees seeking employment opportunities (Galiya Berdykulova et al., 2024).

- Talent Pool Diversification and Employer Branding

It was pointed out in the study that the significance of employer branding and talents pool diversification in a digital recruitment world has been increasingly emphasized. Methods like Employee Testimonials, social media involvement, and company culture videos have worked adequately to demonstrate the distinctive value representation of an organization

and to attract a wide variety of career seekers (Galiya Berdykulova et al., 2024). Organizations can ensure their employer brand and actively engage communities that are underrepresented so they become the place where the best talent wants to work. In turn this can result in a more inclusive and diverse work force, which can spur innovation, greater ability to solve problems, and a more accurate representation of the communities they represent.

- The Role of Digital Recruitment in Retention Strategies

The research results have also noted the importance of retention strategy in total recruitment environment. Such programs as implemented onboarding, mentorship, and wellness programs were noted to be of great importance in retaining the employees and motivating them to continue their work in and with the organization. The effects of the digital recruitment strategies were further reinforced and it was demonstrated in the study that organizations which have been able to successfully adopt digital tools and data-based insights in their recruitment process has been experiencing a tremendous enhancement in their hiring speed, quality of candidates and employee retention (Hoang et al., 2025).

- Trends and Consideration in the Future

In its prospects, the research study has noted a range of emerging trends of considerations that will transform the future of recruitment. It is predicted that technological innovations like AI-enhanced hiring tools and virtual reality job interviews will redefine the process of new talent identification and evaluation and the onboarding process as well (Hoang et al., 2025).

Besides, it emphasizes organizational agility and the need to continually improve the applications of digital recruitment. With the current trends in management of employment, companies that are flexible and progressive in their strategy would be more successful at luring and retaining top talent in future.

5.2 Conclusion

As a result of the research study, the specifics of the digital recruitment environment as well as its challenges are thoroughly understood, and the methods that organizations are using to recruit, engage, and retain the best talent are identified. These were the main findings which underline the centrality of the digital tools, digital platforms and techniques in the contemporary talent acquisition, and the relevance of employer branding, diversification of talent pools and retention tools as the instruments of organizational success. The continuous transformation of the recruitment environment requires the organizations to be agile, dynamic, and dynamic in how they acquire the talent. Only with a data and candidate-focused approach, constant search of creative digital tools, organizations may become an employer of choice, develop a strength and diverse workforce, and eventually attain their strategic targets.

5.3 Recommendations

Buying Digital Tools and Platforms is the first step that organizations should consider when they need to optimize their recruitment strategies in the era of new technologies. With a wide range of applicant tracking systems, social media, and data analytics applications, companies can simplify their recruitment procedures, gain greater involvement and contact with the potential recruits and make more data-driven and informed decisions throughout the talent acquisition process.

It is also vital to improve the Employer Brand by making candidates today more discerning and also to find a unique and memorable value proposition that will provide an organization. Through the digital space such as social media, company websites and the testimonies of employees, organizations can develop a realistic and appealing employer brand that will really speak to their target quality of talent. This will in its turn, give rise to more diverse and highly qualified force of candidates.

The Diversity of the Talent Pool should be one of the priorities of the organizations striving to create a workforce that would be representative of the communities where the organizations are operating. Organizations can proactively contact underrepresented groups, build specific recruitment processes, and work with professional associations, community groups, and higher education facilities in order to access a more extensive

and even broader pipeline. It is also necessary to develop Comprehensive Retention Strategies because digital recruitment activities are no stronger than the organization can recruit, engage, and retain talent they acquire. The implementation of strong onboarding mechanisms, highly organized mentorship programs and employee wellness programs can help in bringing about employee job satisfaction, loyalty and long-term commitment to the cause.

The digital recruitment culture environment is constantly changing, and it is imperative to cultivate a Culture of Adaptability. Organizations should be prepared to conduct perpetual examinations and modification of their online hiring strategies in order to make sure that they are constantly in correspondence with the latest trends, changes as well as the requirements and preferences of applicants.

The ability to leverage Data-Driven Insights is the most significant attribute to optimize on digital recruitment strategies. The potential of digital initiatives lies in the fact that organizations can analyze their performance and engage in data-informed decision-making activities through precise observations that can subsequently optimize their talent acquisition activities. At last, Cooperation between both IT and HR Teams is critical to the effective delivery and subsequent advancement of digital recruitment of an organization. With close collaboration, these two departments will be able to get the much-needed infrastructure, support and continuous development to make the digital recruitment a successful business. These are some of the critical aspects that organizations can consider comprehensively to work as employers of choice, attract and maintain the best perspective.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

Geographical Scope: The study was majorly based on the study of the organizations and job seekers of certain geographical region. The results might not represent the world of recruitment as sufficiently and the additional research could be necessary to understand the specifics of the digital recruitment format in such different cultural and economic realities.

Sample Size and Diversity: The sample on both sides rather the employer or job seeker may have been small and this was a diverse sample. The bigger and more heterogeneous sample would have allowed obtaining more insights and views on the digital approach to recruitment and its effects.

Technological Advances: The speed with which technological advances in the recruitment sector come can have become faster than the extent of the study. Since new digital tools and platforms still emerge, the findings might have to be updated on a regular basis to stay current with the situation.

Qualitative Bias: There was a lot of use of the qualitative data in the study and this can be either biased by the researcher and also have an interpretation. Although they tried to be objective in their research, it might be affected by subjective views and experiences of the researchers.

Longitudinal issues: It was a cross-sectional study that measures the current state of the digital recruitment environment at that particular time. A longitudinal study would be of use in offering some determination into the long-term developments, issues and innovations in the recruitment industry.

5.5 Directions for future researches

Increase Geographical Replication: Repeat the study within other geographical variations to find out cultural, economic, and regulatory forces that can lead to adoption and implementation of digital recruitment strategies in various contexts.

Expand Sample and Vary Types: This variability of the sample should be achieved by conducting a broader study with different types of employers and job seekers to cover a widened variety of approaches and experiences in the field of digital recruitment.

Discover Emerging Technologies: Look into the role of emerging technologies, i.e., artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and blockchain, in the world of recruitment and talent acquisition in the future. Consider their opportunities, challenges, and ethical implications governing the process of integrating such techs.

Longitudinal Analysis: Conduct longitudinal research to monitor how digital recruitment strategies have evolved over time, what are the major drivers of the change and what adaptations organizations have undertaken as well as their long-term impacts on talent acquisition and workforce development.

Comparative Analysis: develop a comparative analysis of Organizations that have been successful versus struggling on implementing digital recruitment strategies. Explore the key success factors, organization capability/ability and the best practice that separates the high performing organizations and those that are not.

Check the Candidate Perspective: Go further into job seeker experience, researching their preferences, expectations and attitudes towards digital process of recruitment. Find out what determines their choices and interest on the digital recruitment initiatives of organizations.

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Appendix 01- Questionnaire

Section 1: Participant Information

- 1. Name:**
- 2. Position/Title:**
- 3. Organization:**
- 4. Years of Experience in Recruitment:**
- 5. Industry:**

Section 2: Interview Questions

- 1. What are the primary digital tools and platforms your organization currently utilizes in the recruitment process?**
- 2. How have these digital tools and platforms impacted the efficiency, candidate quality, and overall effectiveness of your recruitment efforts?**
- 3. What are the key challenges your organization has faced in implementing and integrating digital recruitment strategies?**
- 4. How does your organization approach employer branding and talent pool diversification in the digital recruitment landscape?**
- 5. What specific strategies or initiatives have you implemented to enhance your employer brand and reach a more diverse pool of candidates?**
- 6. How do your retention strategies complement your digital recruitment efforts, and what initiatives have you put in place to keep employees engaged and committed to the organization?**
- 7. In your opinion, what are the emerging trends and future considerations that will shape the digital recruitment landscape in the years to come?**
- 8. How do you envision your organization's digital recruitment strategies evolving to adapt to these anticipated changes?**
- 9. What role do you believe data-driven insights and analytics play in informing and refining your digital recruitment strategies?**
- 10. How do you ensure that your digital recruitment processes and tools align with your overall organizational goals and values?**

11. What advice would you give to other organizations looking to enhance their digital recruitment capabilities and position themselves as employers of choice?

12. Is there anything else you would like to share about your organization's experiences and learnings in the digital recruitment space?

Appendix 02 - Supervision Record Form

<p style="text-align: center;">POSTGRADUATE DISSERTATION SUPERVISION RECORD FORM</p>		
Name of the Student	Bentotage Ravindu Kumara Lankathilanke Lankasena	Student Number 25807865
Programme & the Module	Master of Human Resource Management HRMM030 : Dissertation and Research Methods	
Dissertation Title	Investigating the Effectiveness of the Digitalized Recruitment and Selection Process in Hiring the Best Talent: A Case Study of The Ned Doha Hotel, Qatar	
Name of the Research Supervisor	Ms. Subhani De Silva	

Date	Matters discussed & discussion taken	Signature of the Research Supervisor
08.02.25	Research Proposal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advised to change the target employee category. Advised to amend the research topic according to the target employee category and independent and dependent variables. Advised to change the other sections according to the target employee category. Advised to properly identified the independent and dependent variables. Advised to amend the conceptual framework according to the independent and dependent variables. 	
12.02.25	Research Proposal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advised to clearly state the research gap. Advised to remove the duplicated independent variables from conceptual framework. The research methodology is incorrect. 	
21.02.25	Research Proposal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advised to state the selected organization in the research topic. Advised to state the significance of the study. Advised to clearly state the research problem. Advised to do a literature review for dependent variable. Advised to update the research methodology. 	

14.03.25	<p>Research Proposal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advised to update the research aim as a sentence, not a paragraph. • Advised to revise the research objectives IV • Advised to update Methodology with research approach. • Advised to state the total population, sample size and data analysis techniques. • Advise to update the timeline with months. 	
24.04.25	<p>Research:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advised to update the first sub heading with the chapter introduction. • Advised to mention why particular hotel is relevant for studying these practices. • Advised to focusing on one or two key gaps, especially those directly affecting The Ned Doha Hotel. • Advised to state the central research problem could be stated more clearly and succinctly. • Advised to maintain the flow between points could be improved with clearer transitions. • Advised to state theoretical significance and the practical significance separately. • Advised to change the paragraphs in research questions to view as a questions format. 	
12.06.25	<p>Research:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advised to state at least 03/04 under IV. • Advised to refer literature between 2020 to 2025. • Advised to state the research gap. • Advised to mention the theoretical significance. • Advised to develop research objectives based on the attributes identified under the IV. 	
07.07.25	<p>Research: Individual session with Mr. Sandun</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advised to update the conceptual framework according to the qualitative method. • Advised to align the literature reviews to the research topic, objectives and aim. • Advised to revise first 3 chapters to be align with the conceptual framework and research topic. • Guided regarding the NVivo analysis. 	

Appendix 03 - Organisation Consent

ORGANISATION CONSENT

We hereby grant the permission to Mr. BRKL Lankasena to conduct the Research Study in our organization as a partial fulfillment of his Master's in Human Resource Management Degree from University of Northampton.

I understand that the information obtained by the student about the organization will be kept strictly confidential and only viewed by the student, research supervisors of University of Northampton and Human Resource Management Institute.

Name : Sonia Attouche

Designation : Director of HR

Email Address : sonia.attouche@thened.com

Contact No.s : +974 4406 1111

Signature :

Date :

20.04.20

Official Seal :

